

Some Studies on Thallium Oxalates—VIII : Barium *Bis*-Oxalato Diaquo Thallate(III) Monohydrate

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When about 0.01M thallium(III) in 0.1M HNO₃ is treated with 0.1M oxalic acid in the presence of 0.025M Ba(NO₃)₂ and 0.1M HNO₃, a white crystalline compound is obtained. Chemical analysis of the compound obtained corresponds to the formula, BaTi₂(C₂O₄)₂·5H₂O. Thermal decomposition studies indicate the simultaneous dehydration and redox decomposition of the thallium(III) salt with the formation of an intermediate, BaTi₂(C₂O₄)₂, stable from 150°-290° which finally decomposes to a mixture of barium carbonate and oxides of thallium(I) and thallium(III). Infrared absorption spectra, microscopic observations and X-ray diffraction data are utilised to confirm the proposed mechanism for the thermal decomposition of the compound. Basing on these results the proposed structural formula of the complex is Ba[Tl(C₂O₄)₂(H₂O)₂]₂·H₂O.

CONDITIONS were established¹ for the preparation of *bis*-oxalato diaquo thallate(III) with a metal-ligand ratio of 1 : 1.5. The presence of sufficient concentration of barium ion in the potentiometric titration of thallium(III) with oxalic acid was found to alter the metal-ligand ratio from 1 : 1.5 to 1 : 2². The authors' findings on the preparation and analysis of the resulting solid (obtained in the presence of Ba²⁺), its thermal behaviour, characterisation of the compound and its intermediate products of thermal decomposition using ir absorption, X-ray diffraction and microscopic observations are presented in this article.

Experimental

The experimental details of TG, DTG and DTA measurements, ir, X-ray diffraction and microscopic observations are similar to those already reported³.

Preparation and analysis of the compound : The complex is precipitated using the conditions ([Ba²⁺]=0.025 M; [HNO₃]=0.1 M and [Tl³⁺]=0.01 M) reported earlier³. The white crystalline solid thus obtained is separated using IG 4 sintered glass crucible, washed first with minimum quantity of wash liquid (containing 0.1 M nitric acid and 0.025 M barium nitrate) and finally with acidulated (with nitric acid) water. The compound is dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous silica gel.

The ratio of thallium and oxalate contents of the compound and of the intermediate (obtained by heating the compound at 170°) are found⁴ to be 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 respectively. The ratio of barium and thallium in the intermediate and hence in the original complex is found to be 1 : 2 (by difference). The presence of carbonate in the final product is confirmed by the usual acid test. By thermal studies the original complex is found⁵ to contain 5 moles of water. The chemical analysis data indicates the molecular formula of the compound to be

Ba[Tl(C₂O₄)₂]₂·5H₂O, which is further supported by the following studies.

Thermal decomposition studies : It is evident from the pyrolysis curve (Fig. 1) that the continuous loss from 50° to 150° corresponds to the dehydration (5 moles of water) and redox decomposition of thallic oxalate to thallic oxide (with loss of two moles of oxalate i.e. 4 moles of CO₂). In the DTG curve there are two peaks indicating the step-wise loss in weight between 50° and 150°. The first slope around 100° indicates a gradual and partial dehydration and the loss in weight corresponds to one mole of water suggesting that one mole of water to be different from the rest of the water in the compound. The sharp peak around 140° and the weight of the sample at 160° indicate a rapid decomposition of the compound at this temperature. In the DTA curve a broad endothermic peak with ΔT_{min} around 95° indicates a gradual and partial dehydration while the sharp exothermic peak with ΔT_{max} at 140° indicates a rapid decomposition presumably involving simultaneous dehydration and redox decomposition steps.

The second loss from 270° to 375° in the thermogram corresponds to the decomposition of the intermediate to give rise to a mixture of barium carbonate and thallic oxide. The gain from 375° corresponds to the partial oxidation of thallic oxide to thallic oxide which is thermally stable upto 540°. The peaks in DTG around 370° indicates a sequential loss and gain in weight. The first loss might involve the decomposition of the complex to a mixture of BaCO₃ and Tl₂O as the weight loss tallies for this reaction, while the immediate rise in the peak presumably indicates the subsequent partial oxidation⁶ of the thallic oxide by air⁶. In DTA, a sharp exothermic peak with ΔT_{max} at 370° corresponds to the decomposition of this intermediate to a mixture of barium carbonate and thallic oxide while an exothermic

Fig. 1. T.G., D.T.G. and D.T.A. for the thermal decomposition of barium bis-oxalato thallate(III) pentahydrate.

shoulder with ΔT_{max} at 375° corresponds to the partial oxidation of thallium(I) to thallium(III)⁶.

The above data suggest the following stepwise mechanism for the thermal decomposition of the compound.

From the thermal decomposition data alone it is not possible to ascertain the formulae of the original compound and the intermediate. Hence, the following further studies are carried out.

Infrared absorption spectral studies : The spectra of the compound and the product obtained by heating the compound upto 170° are shown in Figs. 2 and 3. The prominent characteristic peaks due to bending modes of vibration of O=C=O of thallos oxalate⁸ and barium oxalate (ionic compounds) at 770 and 755 cm^{-1} have been shifted in the case of the compound to 795 and 765 cm^{-1} respectively. The shift indicates certainly some

increase in the covalent character of the bond between the central metal, thallium(III), and the oxygen of the ligand, oxalate ion. The very sharp and strong peak at 795 cm^{-1} may be a combination band of carboxylate and coordinated water⁹. Hence, the molecular formula should be either (1) or (2) (a complex) and cannot be $\text{BaC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot \text{Tl}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (a double salt which is ionic).

Very broad and strong absorption peaks⁷ with maxima around 3500 and 3400 cm^{-1} in Fig. 2 indicate the presence of water in the complex in any form (i. e. coordinated or lattice or both) while the absence of these peaks in Fig. 3 indicates the absence of water in the heated product (obtained by heating the complex to 170° and cooling to room temperature). This also confirms that the intermediate does not absorb moisture from atmospheric air even after cooling to room temperature. At this stage it may be worth mentioning that the heated products of other salts such as ammonium⁸ and potassium⁸ absorb moisture.

Microscopic observations : Barium bis-oxalato diaquo thallate(III) monohydrate occurs as prismatic euhedral crystals having high birefringence and showing twinkling effects. Its lower refractive index is 1.604 ± 0.002 and higher refractive index is 1.608 ± 0.002 .

The microscopic observations of the crystals developed from the aqueous solution of the intermediate showed the absence of thallos oxalate⁸. This observation confirms the intermediate to be a single compound $\text{BaTl}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2$ and not a mixture of BaC_2O_4 and $\text{Tl}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$.

Fig. 2. Infrared spectrum of barium bis-oxalato thallate(III).

Fig. 3. Infrared spectrum of barium bis-oxalato thallate(III) after heating to 170° .

TABLE 1—THERMOGRAVIMETRIC DATA OF BARIUM bis-OXALATO THALLATE(III) MONOHYDRATE

Weight of the complex, mg	Step No.	Temperature °C		Loss in weight of the complex, mg		Thermal decomposition reaction proposed
		Starting	Ending	Observed	Calculated	
241	I	50	150	65	64.8	$\text{Ba}[\text{Ti}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{BaTi}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_4$
	II	270	375	24	24.4	$\text{BaTi}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_4 \rightarrow \text{BaCO}_3 + \text{Ti}_2\text{O}_3$
	III	375	380	6	—	$\text{BaCO}_3 + \text{Ti}_2\text{O}_3$
	overall	50	380	83	—	$\text{Ba}[\text{Ti}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{BaCO}_3 + x\text{Ti}_2\text{O}_3 + (1-x)\text{Ti}_2\text{O}_5$

X-ray diffraction data: The X-ray diffraction data of the complex and the intermediate are compared with that of thallos oxalate⁸, $\text{BaC}_2\text{O}_4^{\cdot 0}$ and $\text{BaC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}^{\cdot 0}$. From the comparison it is indicated that both barium oxalate and thallos oxalate are absent in the intermediate. This also confirms the intermediate to be $\text{BaTi}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_4$. The values corresponding to the prominent reflections (6.371₂, 2.797₅ and 4.983₃) of the complex may be made use of in differentiating the barium salt from the other salts of bis-oxalato thallate(III)^{8,9,11-15}.

Conclusion: The thermal analysis results and the probable mechanism for the decomposition of the complex are summarised in Table 1.

Bis-oxalato thallate(III) is reported to be octahedral¹⁶⁻¹⁸ in $\text{H}[\text{Ti}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{K}[\text{Ti}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ on the grounds that the octahedral bonds are stronger than the tetrahedral bonds¹⁸. The same argument may be extended to barium bis-oxalato thallate(III) pentahydrate also. Moreover, the infrared spectral data confirm the presence of coordinated water in the complex suggesting it more likely to be octahedral rather than tetrahedral. The compound may therefore be formulated as :

References

- S. R. SAGI and K. V. RAMANA, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1969, 245, 320.
- S. R. SAGI and K. V. RAMANA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 587.
- S. R. SAGI, K. V. RAMANA and M. S. PRASADA RAO, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1979, 31, 285.
- S. R. SAGI and K. V. RAMANA, *Talanta*, 1969, 16, 1217.
- C. E. MCNEILLY and F. P. ROBERTS, "Thermal Analysis", Vol. 2, "Inorg. Materials and Phys. Chem.", Academic Press N. Y., London, 1969, 727.
- M. D. KARKHANAVALA and S. H. DAROOWALLA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 1112.
- P. J. LUCCHESI and W. A. GLASSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 1347.
- S. R. SAGI, K. V. RAMANA and M. S. PRASADA RAO, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1979, 33, 187.
- J. FUJITA, A. E. MARTELL and K. NAKAMOTO, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1962, 36, 324, 331.
- A. S. T. M. CARDS, X-ray diffraction data.
- S. R. SAGI, K. V. RAMANA and M. S. PRASADA RAO, *J. Thermal Analysis*, 1980, 18, 291.
- S. R. SAGI, K. V. RAMANA and M. S. PRASADA RAO, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1980, 19, 575.
- S. R. SAGI, M. S. PRASADA RAO and K. V. RAMANA, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1980, 40, 311.
- S. R. SAGI, K. V. RAMANA and M. S. PRASADA RAO, *Indian J. Chem.*, (In press).
- S. R. SAGI, K. V. RAMANA and M. S. PRASADA RAO (to be published).
- R. J. MEYER and E. GOLDSCHMIDT, *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 238.
- W. O. RABE and H. STRINMETZ, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 4447; *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1903, 37, 88.
- P. J. DURRANT and B. DURRANT, "Introduction to Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Longmann, 2nd ed., 1969, p. 600.